

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: SWARRAY****FIRST NAME: ANSUMANA LYNTON****PROGRAM CODE : DCCS****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: PERIOD 1****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: MSWord Windows 11 version 22

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Understanding good essay writing (EUCLID 2021, 7-14)
2. The process of academic writing (EUCLID 2021, 7-14)
3. Structuring academic writings (EUCLID 2021, 10)
4. Ensuring good mechanical accuracy (EUCLID 2021, 16)
5. Academic writing style (EUCLID 2021, 41)
6. Avoiding plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 34-36)

DOCTORAL PROGRAMME ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

This piece is a perspective on academic writing from literatures reviewed- the ACA-401D Coursepack and other relevant and authentic literatures. As noted in the Coursepack and Academic Writing: A Handbook for International Students 5th Edition (Bailey 2018), there are many forms of academic writings such as notes, reports, projects, essays, dissertations/theses and papers.

Even though I am conversant with most of these forms of academic writings in over twenty years of academic and professional engagements, doctoral program requires extensive and quality writings, which requires full preparedness for elaborative academic writings and vivid understanding of the theories and mechanics behind a good academic writing. Research writing courses at undergraduate and master's degrees levels are not elaborate as the expectation is that the student should have learnt sufficient English at high school level and from introductory courses at university level. Often, students find academic writing difficult, and panics usually sets in especially when English is not the medium for instruction and communication for most countries. Even when English is the medium for instruction and communication, achieving a good standard of academic writing

is often hard work (Broome 2021). This is why I found this comprehensive preparatory course by EUCLID very useful and appropriate, as it will help me to be grounded and strengthens my language communications, general academic writing mechanics and style.

With this brief introduction, I will now proceed to discuss the following:

- Understanding good essay writing,
- The process of academic writing,
- Structuring academic writings,
- Ensuring good mechanical accuracy,
- Academic writing style, and
- Avoiding plagiarism.

2) UNDERSTANDING GOOD ESSAY WRITING

It is clear in the ACA-401D Coursepack, Academic Writing: Handbook for International Students 5th Edition and Academic Writing: A basic Survival Guide for Students that understanding good essay writing starts with enough reading. I have found out from these literatures that writing a good essay is not a linear process, but cyclical and dynamic that involves good reading and organisation of thought processes. Sufficient reading can lay the foundation for understanding the research or writing area as well as providing the direction and guidance for a good writing. As noted in the Coursepack, there is much emphasis placed on sufficient reading to collect vital information that will support and strengthen your work:

‘It is essential to make some notes while you read, as this will be the basis for your essay. However, in your initial reading photocopies, it is advised you underline or highlight relevant information, which you can return to when you re-read and take notes’ (Euclid 2021, 8).

The Coursepack also emphasized the need to clearly keep the topic or research questions in your mind that will guide the collection and compilation of relevant information for future use. These I found very useful.

3) THE PROCESS OF ACADEMIC WRITING

Academic writing, like any other human endeavors involves processes as explained in the ACA-401 Coursepack (EUCLID 2021, 7-14), A Handbook for International Students 5th Edition (Bailey 2018,10-16) and Academic Writing: A basic Survival Guide for Students (Broome 2021, 3-10). These processes are purpose setting, planning, problem

definition, resource gathering, reading/creative and critical thinking and writing of the essay (EUCLID 2021, 7-14).

On page 13 of the Coursepack, the purpose of the writing should state from the onset (EUCLID 2021, 13). Bailey 2021 identified the following as the common reasons or purpose for academic writings. These should be stated clearly: discussion on a subject of a common interest, synthesis research done by others on a topic, answer to a question that a writer has been given or chosen, and a report an apiece of research a writer has conducted (Bailey 2018, 3). I have also found that even with a clear purpose, a lot of planning, problem definition and other processes are very important to write a good essay. According to Bailey 2018, academic works that require many details must be well planned as early as possible (Bailey 2018, 234). This is quite true with doctoral thesis writing, and that is why I found it essential and necessary that the first module of my doctoral program is an academic writing that will be prepare well for all the writings ahead of me. Writing is a whole project. Therefore, it should well be planned to meet the objectives of the writing.

From the Coursepack and the other literatures reviewed, it is clear to me that a best writing plan will produce an outline that includes the next activities, timelines and how those activities will be done. For instance, I should note here that resource gathering for academic writings is comparison to other forms of writing tends to be cumbersome and requires more details and organization (Broome 2021, 30). In addition to this, it is also clear to me from the Coursepack, and the other literature reviewed that extracting and fine-tuning information from several sources is strenuous and involves creativity and critical thinking (Bailey 2018, 23; Broome 2021, 18; EUCLID 2021, 9). Creative and critical thinking will broaden and deepen your work's horizon and improve and increase its quality (EUCLID 2021, 10). It will make problem definition and analysis to be easy, as well as the organization of your ideas and the writing of the essay (EUCLID 2021, 10).

4) STRUCTURING ACADEMIC WRITINGS

As I mentioned in section three above, one of the processes of academic writing is the organization and putting together of all the ideas and facts generated and synthesized, which is referred to as the writing of the work. I have understood from the literature reviewed that academic writings should be properly structured to be logical and provide clarity, coherence, and cohesion (Bailey 2018, 71-81; Broome 2021, 24; EUCLID 2021, 10). Structures are skeletal or frameworks that inform the readers of the links, direction, and flow of the ideas and how they relate and interact with one another (Bailey 2018, 71-81; Broome 2021, 17; EUCLID 2021, 10). I have found that this is one of the reasons why some writings are more enjoyable and appreciated than others.

Depending on the nature and type of academic writing, academic writing can be structured into broad categories of introduction, body, and conclusions, with each category further structured into smaller units, called paragraphs (Bailey 2018, 71-81; Broome 2021, 17; EUCLID 2021, 10). An interesting point I have learned from these reviews is what should constitute a paragraph and conclusion and how each should be structured (Bailey

2018, 71-81; EUCLID 2021, 10). The idea of a topic sentence that states the main controlling idea of a paragraph (EUCLID 2021, 10) is fascinating to me.

5) ENSURING GOOD MECHANICAL ACCURACY

Another important cardinal point understood from the literature reviewed that ensures clear communication and appreciation of one's writing is the application and adherence to mechanical or technical accuracy. Mechanical or technical accuracy refers to the detailed elements that combine to construct words, sentences, and paragraphs, such as spelling, punctuation, and grammar appropriately (Brown 2021). It is often referred to as the rule of language writing (EUCLID 2021, 16). It is also clear to me from the literatures that quite often, the improper application of the rules of writing creates mechanical or grammatical errors. There is also a stark difference between mechanical errors and grammatical errors. In *Common Mistakes* by the University of Minnesota,

“Grammar is the structure of written or spoken English. It refers to the part of speech and how they combine for form sentences. Mechanics on the other hand, refers to the rules of the written language such as capitalization, punctuations, and spellings” (Lethbridge College, n.d, in Brown 2021)

For instance, a writer must understand the right use of apostrophe in the case of a singular or plural now to indicate possession. The writer should not add an apostrophe with s to a plural noun that ends with s. But if the plural noun does not end with s, in the case of children, the writer must add an s after the apostrophe (EUCLID 2021,16).

6) ACADEMIC WRITING STYLE

Since my graduate education, I have been applying a variant of the Harvard style of writing introduced to me at Loughborough University. Based on what I have read and understood from the Coursepack and other literatures, I am keen of applying the Turabian style (Chicago Rule) of writing that has been introduced to me by EUCLID, which I believe will strengthen and improve on my quality of writing. During my graduate study at the water Engineering and Development Centre (WEDC), Loughborough University, I was introduced to a variant of the Harvard writing style.

It is also clear from the Coursepack (EUCLID 2021, 41) that even though there is no single authoritative source on style on written language, and most often, the style of writing depends on the sphere of writing (technical, commercial, journalism, or web copywriting, etc.), there is a common understanding amongst all that style should encompass the following: objectivity, to be impersonal, punctuation, grammar, vocabulary, preferred sentence length, manuscript layout, spelling, font usage, readers consideration, use of abbreviation and symbols, etc. (EUCLID 202, 41). Clarity, coherence, and consistency are very important keys in academic writing, and the style should meet the consistency objective.

7) AVOIDING PLAGIARISM

It is worth noting here that most human efforts require the upholding of moral and ethical values. Moral and ethical values demand the recognition and respect of one's efforts, views, and standpoints. This is why in my opinion; plagiarism is one of the great offences in the learning and writing circle. It is well documented in the Coursepack (EUCLID 2021, 34-36) and other documents reviewed how to write a good essay while avoiding embarrassment from plagiarism. To avoid reputational damage, crediting the efforts of others is non-negotiable and unforgivable in the academic world. The emphasis on plagiarism in the Coursepack and the other literatures read has excited my ethical consciousness.

It is also worth noting that there are degrees of plagiarism, according to Academic Writing: Handbook for International Students 5th Edition (Bailey 2018,27-28). For instance, technical plagiarism is a situation when an author's name is misspelled in the citation. This is more of carelessness on the part of the writer. Self-plagiarism is also possible if you fail to provide correct reference to a previous work that you did. Plagiarism can be avoided by paraphrasing, summarizing, and developing good study habit (EUCLID 2021, 36; Bailey 2018, 27-30)

8) CONCLUSION

It is clear from the literature reviewed that writing a good academic paper involves the consideration of rules, skills, processes, and preferences. To become a good or renowned writers, these writing values and norms must be upheld.

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